

Current Status: ALPHA (Stage 3/4)

The current status of the project is that Stage 3 is *ideally* complete and Stage 4 is about to commence. Details of preceding stages are provided in Table 1 while Table 2 outlines the timetable for the project.

Table 1: Data provided at each stage.

Stage	Forcing data	Built and veg. cover %	Urban morphology details	Details of Urban Materials
1	✓			
1.5	✓	✓		
2	✓	✓	✓	
3	✓	✓	✓	✓
4	Observed fluxes provided and site revealed			

Table 2: Planned timetable

Target date	Objective	Status
1 Mar	Outputs of test data returned	Complete
1 April	First dataset released (Stage 1)	Complete
30 April	Deadline for return of Stage 1 output	On-going
1 May	Land cover data issued (Stage 1.5)*	On-going
31 May	Deadline for return of Stage 1.5 output	On-going
1 June	Urban morph. data issued (Stage 2)*	On-going
30 June	Deadline for return of Stage 2 output	On-going
1 July	Urban materials data issued (Stage 3)	On-going
1 Aug	All site data released (Stage 4)	Commencing

* Note: subsequent data only released following receipt of output from the previous Stage.

For Stage 4, participants will be issued with ALL data available concerning the site from which the alpha dataset were obtained. This will consist not only of the location of the urban site but of detailed characteristics of its urban environment. Participants will also be free to conduct their own research to add to the information we circulate, although where this is conducted, we request that full details of all information and parameters utilised are returned to us **in addition to** the actual output data.

To aid analysis of the data you have provided us with over preceding Stages, we are keen to know where each group assumed the location of the site to be when they are assigned parameter values. As such, prior to receiving the data for this final stage, we ask participants to contact us with this information.

As before, please do not share any information with any other participating group. The data also cannot be used for other purposes.

For participants not currently at Stage 4 (details of the stage that each group is at are displayed in Table 4), please endeavour to return the output of your models to us as soon as possible – **this includes corresponding timestamp information and parameter details**. Please make us aware of any potential inaccuracies in Table 4.

If you have not confirmed the accuracy of the statistical plots, you have received individually, the plots and the **parameter plots** included in the newsletters 5 -7 please do so as these are the ones that will be reported publicly.

If you have questions, please consult the FAQ section of Newsletter 6 (July, 2008) or contact us at UrbanMet@kcl.ac.uk.

If you have submitted an Abstract for this session please you let us know.

Abstracts submitted for consideration for the:

AMS Annual Meeting, January 2009, Phoenix

An international urban surface energy balance model comparison study: first results.

Grimmond, S., Blackett, M. and Best, M.

with Baik, J., Bohnenstengel, S., Calmet, I., Chemel, C., Chen, F., Dandou, A., Fortuniak, K., Gouvea, M., Hamdi, R., Kondo, H., Krayenhoff, S., Lee, S., Loridan, T., Martilli, A., Masson, V., Miao, S., Oleson, K., Pigeon, G., Porson, A., Salamanca, F., Shashua-Bar, L., Steeveheld, G., Sugar, L., Trombou, M., Voogt, J., Zhang N.

There are now a number of urban models within the community, which vary in complexity from simple schemes to the detailed representation of momentum and energy fluxes, even distributed within the atmospheric boundary layer. In addition to variations in complexity, these models also differ in parameter requirements and on a more practical level, the cost of running the models. Whilst many of these models have been validated against observational datasets, with some models even using the same observations, these have not been done in a controlled experiment that enables comparisons to be made between the models. Such controlled experiments, however, have been shown in the past to provide scientific insight into both the mechanics of the models and also the physics of the real world, for instance the PILPS experiments. This presentation will describe the progress that has been made so far with regards to an urban model comparison project.

Is there really an optimal solution for model simulations of the urban environment?

Best MJ, M. Hendry

Many parameters within an urban model have uncertainty estimates which could potentially have impacts on the quality of the simulations. Given observational data, it should be possible to optimise these parameters to give the most accurate solution. However, in the simplest urban model design there are a number of fluxes that contribute to the energy balance. So which of these fluxes should be used for an optimisation? Whilst the answer to this question depends upon the application of the model, the impact on the accuracy of the non optimised fluxes is not obvious? As part of the urban model comparison experiments, the Joint UK Land Environment Simulator (JULES) has been optimised on different combinations of the fluxes that contribute to the surface energy balance. The impact of these optimisations on the accuracy of all of the components of the energy balance will be discussed, along with the spread of the resultant parameters within the model. This spread in parameter values will also be considered relative to a priori uncertainties that can be established based upon observations.

Inclusion of a multi-layer drag approach in urban surface schemes: which benefits?

Masson V, R Hamdi, and G Pigeon

The intercomparison exercise allows analysis of the impacts of the main differences between the physics in the models (e.g. chosen geometry, heat transfer equations, canopy air discretization, building discretization, radiation and turbulent exchanges...). However, this can sometimes be difficult due to the fact that several physical formulations are different between models, not allowing to separate clearly the role of each parameterization choice.

Here is presented an improvement of the TEB scheme, with a multi-layer approach for the in and above canopy air. This is a major change in the type of model (from single layer to multilayer), while keeping the same other approximations. The formulation to include air prognostic layers in the surface scheme is derived from the atmospheric equations. New variables are wind, temperature, humidity and Turbulent Kinetic Energy. In TEB, drag forces are added, the heat fluxes by buildings interacts on each of the layers intersecting those, and they modify the Tke equation. The impact of the atmospheric layers is then presented, using the intercomparison exercise data (for which the two versions of TEB were used).

The proposed method of inclusion prognostic atmospheric layer inside TEB (or other surface scheme) allows a finer vertical resolution of the atmosphere (down to the road surface), while keeping a simple way to couple the surface scheme with and the numerical efficiency of the atmospheric models above.

How do initial assumptions for parameters and state variables influence accuracy?

Hendry, M, M.J. Best, M. Gouvea, CSB Grimmond.

When undertaking simulations of the urban environment, it is not possible to have advanced knowledge of the values for all parameters and state variables that are required for initialisation. Hence assumptions have to be made in order to proceed. Usually, the impacts of such assumptions are either neglected, or dismissed as being unimportant. As part of the urban model comparison experiment, the Joint UK Land Environment Simulator (JULES) has been run by a number of people with varying initial assumptions for the different parameters. Also, additional simulations have been undertaken which vary some of the state variables with long term memory (such as soil moisture and temperatures). Fluxes from this set of simulations have been compared against observations to assess the spread of results and quantify the uncertainty in the accuracy of the predictions. The results of this analysis will be presented, along with the implications for global simulations of urban areas which include a diverse spread of parameter values.

Ranking of results for VL92 Stage

The remainder of this newsletter presents summary from the VL92 Stage. Details of what is plotted are summarized in Tables 3 and 4. Note that the statistics were defined in Newsletter 5 (June, 2008).

Here the statistics are *ranked* to aid comparison of the performance of each model. Please take note of the following:

- To ensure anonymity, these data are plotted by model number. Each participant should be aware of their model number but if unsure, please contact us.
- If you see *any problems* with the data plotted for your model, please let us know. This includes its grouping (see Figures 13-15).
- If you wish to resubmit your VL92 results, please let us know.
- Table 4 identifies the most desirable result for each statistic.

Table 3: Summary of plots from the VL92 Stage.

Figure	Description
Ranked results for all models for each flux (Q^* , ΔQ_S , Q_H , Q_{LE}) for the following statistics for the entire time period (n=312):	
1	Mean
2	Standard deviation
3	R^2
4	Root mean square error (RMSE)
5	Index of agreement
6	Mean Average Error (MAE)
7	Mean Bias Error (MBE)
8	Systematic RMSE
9	Unsystematic RMSE
Ranked mean from all models for the fluxes Q^* , ΔQ_S , Q_H , Q_{LE} the following time periods:	
10	Day-time (n=120)
11	Night-time (n=114)
12	Transition period (n=78)
Ranked RMSE for all models for the fluxes Q^* , ΔQ_S , Q_H , Q_{LE} for the entire time period, grouped by the following:	
13	Approach taken to vegetation a) vegetation is integrated b) vegetation is treated in a separate tile so there is no interaction c) not considered
14	Treatment of the urban surface as a slab, single-layer or multi-layer
15	Treatment of facets a) does not resolve facets (i.e. whole) b) resolves roof, wall and road facets but without orientation c) resolves roof, wall and road facets but with orientation (i.e. sunlit, shaded)

- The time periods are defined:

Transition: $[Q^*_{t,t+1} < 0 + Q^*_{t+2} >= 0]$

$[Q^*_{t,t+1} < 0 + Q^*_{t+2} <= 0]$

Else when

$Q^*_t > 0$ **Day**

$Q^*_t < 0 \Rightarrow$ **Night**

where observed Q^* for $t =$ time-step.

Table 4: Ideal statistical characteristics that a model might display.

Statistic	Most desirable value
Mean	Same as the observed mean
sd	Same as the observed mean
R^2	1.0
RMSE	0 W m^{-2}
Index of agreement	1.0
MAE	0 W m^{-2}
MBE	0 W m^{-2}
Systematic RMSE	0 W m^{-2} Smaller than RMSE unsystematic
Unsystematic RMSE	0 W m^{-2}

Sue Grimmond & Matthew Blackett
Department of Geography, King's College London

This project contributes to:

Figure 1: Ranked mean for all models for each flux (Q^* , ΔQ_S , Q_H , Q_{LE}) for the entire time period (n=312). Horizontal lines show the observed data.

Figure 2: Ranked standard deviation for all models for each flux (Q^* , ΔQ_S , Q_H , Q_{LE}) for the entire time period (n=312). Horizontal lines show the observed data.

Figure 3: Ranked R^2 for the whole modelled period for Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_H , Q_{LE} .

Figure 4: Ranked RMSE for the whole period for Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_H , Q_{LE} .

Figure 5: Ranked Index of agreement for the whole period for Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_H , Q_{LE} .

Figure 6: Ranked MAE for the whole period for Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_H , Q_{LE} .

Figure 7. Ranked MBE for the whole period for Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_H , Q_{LE} .

Figure 8: Ranked systematic RMSE for the whole period for Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_H , Q_{LE} .

Figure 9: Ranked unsystematic RMSE for the whole period for Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_H , Q_{LE} .

Figure 10: Ranked mean for the day-time period for Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_H , Q_{LE} . The horizontal line is the observed mean.

Figure 11: Ranked mean for the night-time period for Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_H , Q_{LE} . The horizontal line is the observed mean.

Figure 12: Ranked mean for the transition period for Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_H , Q_{LE} . The horizontal line is the observed mean.

Figure 13: Ranked RMSE grouped by approach to vegetation for Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_H , Q_{LE} , for the entire time period.

Figure 14: Ranked RMSE grouped by how the surface is treated with respect to layers Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_H , Q_{LE} , for the entire period.

Figure 15: Ranked RMSE grouped by what aspects of the surface are explicitly modelled for Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_H , Q_{LE} , for the entire period. R,W,R is roof, wall roads. w/Orient is with orientation, w/out Orient is without orientation.

Table 4. Groups participating and their current status

Model	VL92 data verified?*	VL92 parameters received?	Stage 1 output received?	Stage 1 parameters received?	Stage 1.5 data returned?	Stage 1.5 Parameters returned?	Stage 2 data returned?	Stage 2 parameters returned?	Stage 3 data returned?	Stage 3 parameters returned?
11		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓				
12		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓				
13					Data not released					
14	✓		Data not released							
15			Data not released							
16		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
17		✓	✓	✓	✓					
18			Data not released							
20			Data not released							
21		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		
22		✓	✓		✓					
25		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
26					Data not released					
28		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓				
30		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		
31		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
32	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
33		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		
35	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
36		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			
37					Data not released					
39		✓	✓	✓						
41		✓	Data not released							
42	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
43	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓			
46		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
47		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓				
49		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		
50		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		

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